

Effective Time Management and the Survival of Agricultural Farms In Nigeria

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Abstract:- The study accessed the impact of effective time management on the survival of Agricultural farms in Nigeria in order to get adequate information on the impact of the effective time management on the survival of the Agricultural farms selected for this study.

The study made use of primary data. The data was collected with the use of questionnaire from the Big 4 selected Agricultural farms in Oyo State, South West, Nigeria. The data collected covered the period of 6 years, (2016-2021). Information for the study was extracted from the questionnaire distributed and collected from the staff of the companies selected. The data were analysed using descriptive and quantitative techniques with the use of percentages and tables for fair reporting and illustrations.

It was shown by the result of the study that effective time management has significant influence on the survival of Agricultural farms.

It was concluded by the study that effective time management has great and significant influence on the survival of Agricultural farms in Nigeria.

Keywords:- Effective, Time management, survival, Agricultural farms.

I. INTRODUCTION

Time is a factor that every living soul has to reckon with in life either in business or in ways of life. Infact, it is in this line that an adage says and quoted "A stitch in time saves nine". An article in one of Home Library Organisation Behaviour Journal, (2020) quoted expatriate time management as "Time and Tide wait for None". It emphasizes that an individual should understand the value of time for him to succeed in all aspects of life. People who waste time are the ones who fail to create an identity of their own. (Mark Pettit, 2020), specifies the benefits of time management as better habits and greater productivity.

Improved time management increases focus, builds confidence, and allows one to plan for time more effectively. Effective time management helps leaders, entrepreneurs, and small business owners to achieve their goals. Managing time wisely improves work-life balance and increases happiness. It also reduces stress and allows one to achieve goals faster and easier within the stipulated time frame. He significantly emphasizes that managing time helps to capture bigger opportunities, and it helps to maximize strengths and plan for future days efficiently and effectively.

To survive and succeed in the competitive world in today's increasingly hostile and fast-moving business environment, organizations have to manage time efficiently and effectively. Proper management of time plays a vital role in motivating the employees and thus improving the overall performance of the organization (Channar, Shaikh, Pathan & Mughal, 2014). The competitive environment we live in today encourages people from as early as their elementary education to plan and manage time effectively. The high performance required by competitive conditions forces organizations and directors to use time effectively and stipulates the search to control time (Pehlivan, 2013). Consequently, time is a necessity for every organization in achieving its goals and objectives.

Time management involves keeping a schedule of the tasks and activities that have been deemed important. Keeping a calendar or daily planner is helpful to stay on task, but self-discipline is also required. The most efficient "to-do" list in the world will not help someone who does not look at or follow his daily time planner. (Ojokuku & Obasan, 2011). Time management is the optimized usage of time to achieve easier life. It is a tool that consists of a wide set of rules and personal skills that impact directly stress mitigation in workplaces, families, and social ambiances (Akhavan & Eynolghozat, 2013). It is also the key to high-performance levels and affecting not only the productivity

of employees but also helps to cope with pressure more efficiently (El-Shaer, 2015).

It is instructive to note that time management is one of the necessary conditions for managers' efficiency and effectiveness, and also one of the strategies for improving the conditions of organization survival. Effective Time management can be established in an organization successfully if the appropriate cultural backgrounds are already in place for the system. Therefore, organization should be able to establish an appropriate culture for effective execution of time management and make progress accordingly (El-Shaer, 2015; Iz & Özen, 2010). Time management skills helps managers to better utilize their scarce time resources, allow them to put their attention on the matters of highest priority results improved job performance (Valleria, 2009).

Bill.T. (2020) gives some reasons why time management is important in an organization, some of his minds are managing your time gives a sense of fulfillment. It relieves stress, it also improves self-discipline, improves the ability to make decision, and create productivity and efficiency. However, in his article, he also emphasizes the undesirable consequences of falling to manage time effectively as inefficient work flow, poor work quality can be a challenge when the workers are rushing to bit the time more of her time must have been wasted on other things which eventually may cause higher stress levels. He also stated that not managing time well can lead to missing the deadline of supplying finished products to the customer which eventually may cause a decrease in profitability.

Despite the significance of time management, organizations do not treat time management as an essential ingredient of survival (Adebisi, 2013). Empirical evidence shows the existence of a positive relationship between the use of time and key outcomes such as physical health, psychological well-being, job satisfaction, productivity, and effectiveness (Chang & Nguyen, 2011; Adebisi, 2013). However, finding a relation between organizational survival and time management is the major aim of this research.

Over the last decade, the Nigerian business environment has experienced unsatisfactory progress resulting in retarded growth rate in terms of the economy, a high rate of unemployment particularly among the youths, and low industrial productivity, coupled with a decline in demand (Oginni & Adesanya, 2013). The interaction between industrial representatives and government agencies has kept on nose-diving virtually in all issues, over-exercising control through many rules and regulations with difficult conditions, tax, and other policies with no enough provision for infrastructural facilities that will facilitate business operations (Oginni & Adesanya, 2013). Giving all these challenges, it is difficult for business organizations to respond effectively to their main operational purpose of profit maximization and survival.

In response to these challenges, some organizations have adopted time management to adapt to various pressures facing them. Although scholars like Ojokuku & Obasan

(2011), Adejo (2012), Adebisi (2013), Channar, Shaikh, Pathan & Mughal (2014), have conducted studies on time management, the results from such few studies remain inconclusive. Most of these studies did not attempt to empirically analyze time management as a tool for organizational survival in various companies. Previous attempts focused particularly on character development, organizational culture, employee productivity, and organizational performance. It is on this premise that this study will try to address the identified gap in the literature.

In time management, a lot of challenges have affected the organization in not meeting or cause inefficient work flow, according to (Maja Misis in his journal of 19th March 2021) he significantly disclosed some of the challenges as too many tasks in our schedule. He emphasizes that we should admit that there are always more tasks that we need to do than we think which can be solved by identifying the time required to finish each task before jotting them down in our diary.

Secondly, too many interruptions by receiving a phone call, unscheduled visits, and being distracted by unnecessary issues are the top interruptions encountered in time management. Lack of priority can also affect time management in the sense that, some tasks are important but not urgent. The urgent tasks should be on top of the list. otherwise, one might end up consuming time on something less urgent and important.

Procrastination is another challenge, this is prevail by delaying any of our tasks for tomorrow. In this manner, we are losing our precious time of now and tomorrow when a task is delayed. In his article, he evaluates the fear of failure as another challenge. When afraid of working on a task, two problems may occur. in this case, an unnecessary delay may lead to thinking. perhaps, once you know that you must do the job, then, the task must do at the right time. In this work again, he talks about the lack of organization or proper tasks in our work environment which may become another challenge because the more organized you are, the more focused you become. In another dimension, a lack of strategic direction can also lead to a centralized working system. To survive in an organization, one needs to delegate or ignore any task that is not urgent.

Despite the significance of time management, a lack of enough courage to say "NO" to some tasks can present a big problem for effective time management. One needs to think about how much time he has and when and where he fits it in his schedule before saying "YES".

In conclusion, from all these analyses, empirical evidence shows that time management has a significant effect on employee efficiency, aids the survival of an organization, and likewise has a strong significance in organization profitability.

The effect of time management on productivity purpose is numerous according to Adejo Adeyinka Lawrence (2012) the more efficiently time is managed by the employee of an organization, the more productive and effective the organization become. Proper managing of time

plays a vital role in motivating the employees and thus improving the performance of the organization. The organization faces several problems and challenges centering on inefficiencies in its time management. He emphasizes some of these problems as: lack of job security and poor working conditions of employees, lack of adequate maintenance of human resources policy, lack of proper structuring of the organization which is required to have a new trend that would enhance its efficiency and make it feasible, poor team building and lack of self-discipline. In his final analysis, he describes time as an essential resource every manager needs to achieve the goals and objectives of an organization. It is so delicate that it cannot be saved, drawn back, stopped, retained, or regained but can only be spent at once.

The main objective of the study is to examine the effect of time management on the survival of small scale businesses in Nigeria on life stock farming.

However, for the meaningful and convenient accomplishment of this study, five live stock farms were selected in Oyo State. It is assumed that the information and data collected for this research will be adequate for reasonable generalization.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

To the understanding of the concept of time management, several theories could be applied. However, this study is anchored on two theories, the Pareto theory of 80-20 Rule and theory of effective management. Vilfredo Pareto was an Italian economist and philosopher who formulated the 80-20 rule. His observations were based on the fact that 80% of the land in Italy was owned by 20% of the population. His research work became the thumb rule of many business organizations, where 80% of productivity came from 20% of working employees. This 20% comprised the most efficient people who conducted their work within a specific period, thereby contributing to a high rate of productivity. Based on this theory, business and quality management pioneer, Dr. Joseph Juran said that 'vital few, trivial many' build organizations.

The 80-20 rule could be applied everywhere where time plays a major role to uplift productivity and success of organizations. The key element of this theory is the 20% that matters the most. If you consider all the things that you are doing the entire day, you will find out that it is 20% of your work that produces the net result. Thus, you should try different ways that will allow you to effectively manage the minor portion (Njagi & Malel, 2012). Moreover, the relevance of this theory to time management is that it allows an individual to manage his or her limited time daily productively, as you have to categorize your work and activities for achieving the goals.

The theory on the principle of effective management and organization is important for this study because of its relevance to a proper organization which is a requirement for time management. The theory advanced the philosophy that viewed administration as a technical problem concerned with the division of labor and specialization of functions, the

establishment of a hierarchy of authority, and the span of control.

III. METHODOLOGY

Secondary data was used for this study. Data was collected from the selected big 4 Agricultural farms in Oyo State, South West of Nigeria and the data for the period 2016 and 2021 was used. The Agricultural farms selected were Obasanjo Farms Nigeria Ltd, Lanlated, Ajanla Farms Nigeria Ltd, Ibadan, Niji Farms Nigeria Ltd, Ilero and Ilaji Farms Nigeria Ltd, Ibadan. They specialized in the production and distribution of poultry and piggery products in wholesale and retail quantities in Nigeria. Their product includes; golden chicken, eggs, broilers, breeders, chicken laps, smoked chicken, piglets, cassava, maize, and water Mellon. which are supplied to many supermarkets, Hotels, and Restaurants. The companies have whole sales offices and retail outlets throughout the State.

The Data collected was subjected to descriptive and quantitative analysis. Descriptive statistics such as frequency and percentages to examine the opinion of the respondents was achieved using SPSS. Also, cross-tabulation was done on the variables to produce the result of the chi-square analysis, which is the measure of the significance of the relationship between the two variables, time management and organizational survival.

Therefore, the chi-square was used to calculate using the formula below:

$$X^2 = \sum \left[\frac{(O - E)^2}{E} \right]$$

Where, χ^2 = chi-square

O = Observed frequencies

E = Expected frequencies

At the final level of analysis (the multivariate level) appropriate statistical technique which is binary logistics regression to see the relationship or association between the adjusted and unadjusted explanatory variable (time management), and the dependent variable (organizational survival). In assessing the strength of the association between the dependent and independent variables. All the analysis was done on a 5% significance level, i.e., 95% confidence level, which was adapted based on the general and acceptable standard in social science.

IV. DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

Table 4.1 represents the distribution of the socio-demographic variables of the respondents. The table reveals majority 85.5% were male while 14.5% were female. With regards to age, 39.0% were between 31-40 years, 37.0% between 20-30 years, 13.5% between 41-50 years, 8.5% were between 51 years or more and just 2.0% were below 20 years. Also, the majority 75.0% of the respondents were married and 25.0% single. Furthermore, the highest qualification 44.5% among the respondents was SSCE, 29.0% HND/BSc, and 26.5% were ND/NCE. With regards to the position held, 26.0% were supervisors, 24.5% engineers,

11.0% machine operators, 9.5% staff, 6.5% attendants and technicians respectively while 5.5% were foremen, 4.0% storekeepers and sanitation while just 2.5% were managers. Table 4.1 also showed the majority 57.5% belong to the production unit, 21.0% distribution unit, 12.5% to sales, and 9.0% to other units. With regards to the number of years in the organization, 47.5% had spent between 1-5years, 23.0% between 6-10years, 10.5% were between 11-15years and 16-20years respectively and just 8.5% were between 21-

30years. The majority 70.5% of the respondents were employed full-time, 23.0% part-time and 6.5% were contract staff. Also, 49.5% speak the Yoruba language, 39.5% English, and just 11% speak Igbo. With regards to religion majority, 61.5% were Christian, while 38.5% were Muslim. Finally, the ethnicity distribution showed that the majority 68.5% were Yoruba, 14.5% Igbo, 9.0% of another ethnicity, and 8.0% Hausa.

Variable	Parameter	Frequency	Percent
Gender	Male	171	85.5
	Female	29	14.5
	Total	200	100.0
Age	Below 20	4	2.0
	20-30 years	74	37.0
	31-40 years	78	39.0
	41-50 years	27	13.5
	51 and above	17	8.5
	Total	200	100.0
Marital Status	Single	50	25.0
	Married	150	75.0
	Total	200	100.0
Qualifications	SSCE	89	44.5
	ND/NCE	53	26.5
	HND/B.Sc	58	29.0
	Total	200	100.0
Position Held	Supervisor	52	26.0
	Machine Operator	22	11.0
	Foreman	11	5.5
	Staff	19	9.5
	Store Keeper	8	4.0
	Technician	13	6.5
	Sanitation	8	4.0
	Attendant	13	6.5
	Engineer	49	24.5
	Manager	5	2.5
	Total	200	100.0
Unit Department	Production	115	57.5
	Distribution	42	21.0
	Sales	25	12.5
	procurement (Others)	18	9.0
	Total	200	100.0
Number of year in the organization	1-5 years	95	47.5
	6-10 years	46	23.0
	11-15 years	21	10.5
	16-20 years	21	10.5
	21-30 years	17	8.5
	Total	200	100.0
Employment type	Full Time	141	70.5
	Part Time	46	23.0
	Contract	13	6.5
	Total	200	100.0
Language	English	79	39.5
	Yoruba	99	49.5
	Igbo	22	11.0
	Total	200	100.0
Religion	Christian	123	61.5
	Muslim	77	38.5
	Total	200	100.0

Ethnicity	Yoruba	137	68.5
	Hausa	16	8.0
	Igbo	29	14.5
	Other	18	9.0
	Total	200	100.0

Table 1: Socio-Demographic information

Fig. 1: Distribution of respondents by Gender

Fig. 2: Distribution of respondents by Age

Fig. 3: Distribution of respondents by Marital Status

Fig. 4: Distribution of respondents by Qualification

Fig. 5: Distribution of respondents by Position held

Fig. 6: Distribution of respondents by Unit Department

Fig. 7: Distribution of respondents by Number of year in the organization

Fig. 8: Distribution of respondents by Employment type

Fig. 9: Distribution of respondents by Language

Fig. 10: Distribution of respondents by Religion

Fig. 11: Distribution of respondents by Ethnicity

V. DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

Table 2 presents the respondent's responses to the adopted time management strategy in selected farms. Table 2 showed that the majority 94.2% said the organization set a target for each day to serve as a measure for the workers, 97.5% said the organization has a long-run organizational goal, 94.0% said the organization enforces supervision of its workers to accomplish the target goals. Also, 91.0% said the organization regularly informs the workers to have a clear idea of its goals, 96.0% say the company rank or prioritizes its needs to aid productivity, 88.5% said the organization generally adopts time management strategies while 96.0%

said the organization quickly respond to issues that arise unexpectedly and 86.5% said the organization regularly review the result and compare with the target objectives to identify the gap. Finally, 100% said the organization always thinks of a better way to improve performance and 95.5% said the organization always implements time management strategies. In addition, 100% agreed that management of time helps to increase the profitability of the organization, and it helps in improving ideas of innovation.

In another opinion, 85% agreed that maximum productivity is achieved for the organization through the procurement process, while 15% say NO.

Variable	Yes(%)	No (%)
The organization set a target for each day to serve as a measure for the workers	94.5	5.5
The organization has a long-run organizational goal	97.5	2.5
The organization enforces supervision of its workers to accomplish the target goals	94.0	6
The organization regularly informs the workers to have a clear idea of its goals	91.0	9
The company's rank or prioritize needs to aid productivity	96.0	4
Does the organization generally adopt time management strategies?	88.5	11.5
The organization quickly responds to issues that arise unexpectedly	96.0	4
The organization regularly review the result and compare them with the target objectives to identify the gap	86.5	13.5
The organization always thinks of a better way to improve the performance	100.0	0
The organization always implements the time management strategies	95.5	4.5

Table 2: Adopted Time Management Strategy on productivity

Source: Researcher's Computation 2021

Table 3 showed the relationship between time management and employee efficiency. The table shows an overall very strong relationship between time management and employee efficiency with a grand mean of 4.7 on a 5 point scale. Top among the variables reveals Time management helps to improve employee efficiency (mean=4.8) and Effective time management helps the

employee to achieve up to expectations (mean=4.8). Others include Effective time management helps to increase output (mean=4.7), Effective time management help to achieve an optimal result (mean=4.7), The organizational culture encourages time management for the employee (mean=4.6) and Time management helps to increase the sales level (mean=4.6)

Variable	SD	D	UN	A	SA	Mean	SD
Time management helps to improve employee efficiency	0(0.0)	9(4.5)	0(0.0)	17(8.5)	174(87.0)	4.8	0.7
Effective time management helps to increase output	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	65(32.5)	135(67.5)	4.7	0.5
The organizational culture encourages time management for the employee	0(0.0)	9(4.5)	0(0.0)	56(28.0)	135(67.5)	4.6	0.7
Time management helps to increase the sales level	0(0.0)	9(4.5)	0(0.0)	51(25.5)	140(70.0)	4.6	0.7
Effective time management helps the employee to achieve up to expectation	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	5(2.5)	36(18.0)	159(79.5)	4.8	0.5
Effective time management help to achieve an optimal result	0(0.0)	9(4.5)	0(0.0)	35(17.5)	159(78.0)	4.7	0.7
Grand Mean						4.7	

Table 3: Relationship between time management and employee efficiency

Source: Researcher's Computation 2021

Table 4 show the effect of time management on the survival of the organization. The majority 100% of the respondent said the time management strategy adopted by the organization helps to accomplish tasks efficiently, 82.0% said Time management help to deliver more quality products, and 97.5% said Time management help to gain more customer loyalty. Also, 85.0% said Time management help to gain more employee loyalty and improved productivity, 95.5 said Time management help to provide a

quick response to unexpected matters, Time management help to increase the profitability of the organization, and Time management make the organization stand-out in the industry and Time management impact on overall survival of the organization respectively and 91.0% said Time management help to improve more on ideas and innovation.

Variable	Yes (%)	No (%)
The time management strategy adopted by the organization helps to accomplish tasks efficiently	100.0	0.0
Time management help to deliver more quality products.	82.0	18
Time management help to gain more customer loyalty.	97.5	2.5
Time management help to gain more employee loyalty and improved productivity.	85.0	15.0
Time management help to provide a quick response to unexpected matters	95.5	4.5
Time management help to increase the profitability of the organization	95.5	4.5
Does time management make the organization stand-out in the industry?	95.5	4.5
Time management help to improve more on ideas and innovation	91.0	9.0
Time management impact on overall survival of the organization	95.5	4.5
Time management help to avoid and overcome challenges	95.5	4.5

Table 4: Effect of time management on the survival of the organization.

Source: Researcher’s Computation 2022

Table 5 show the effects of time management practices on organization profitability. The majority of 100% of the respondents said time management help to increase the profitability of the organization. 85% said time

management helps to improve more ideas of innovation while 15% disagreed. 70% agreed that time management help avoids and overcome challenges and 30% disagreed.

Variable	Yes (%)	No (%)
Time management help to increase the profitability of the organization	100.0	0.0
Time management help to improve more ideas of innovation	85.0	15.0
Time management help to avoid and overcome challenges	70.0	30.0

Table 5: Relationship between time management practices and organization profitability of the organization.

Table 6: shows the effect of time management practices on the procurement unit of the organization. The majority of the respondents agreed that time management allows procurement professionals to organize (100%). They also agreed that time management enables staff to get more done in less time because, with the organized procurement unit, materials needed would have been on the ground for immediate replacement if the need be. 75% agreed that time

management help streamlines its procurement strategy, while 25% disagreed. The argument on this is that strategies can only work where a functional strategic level is adopted. 95% agreed that maximum productivity can be achieved for the organization through the procurement process, while a minority of 5% disagreed. Lastly, the majority of the respondents agreed (100%) that procurement should be part of any time management strategy.

Variable	Yes (%)	No (%)
Time management procurement professionals to organize	100.0	0.0
Time management enables staff to get more done in less time	100.0	0.0
Time management help to streamline its procurement strategy	75.0	25.0
Maximum productivity is achieved for the organization through the procurement process	95.0	5.0
Procurement should be part of any time management strategy	100.0	0.0

Table 6: Effect of time management and procurement unit of the organization

Table 5 shows an overall percentage of 100% of the respondents that time management has a strong relationship with the performance of organization productivity. All other respondents agreed that time management has relatively significant with 91% and above. Also, 96% agreed that time management prioritizes needs to aid productivity and all strategies put in place on productivity based on time management have positive effects. Therefore, time

management has a significant on organization productivity, while the null hypothesis is rejected the alternative is accepted.

Table 6 Respondents agreed that time management has a strong significant relationship with the practice of procurement in an organization with a larger percentage of 100%. The majority also agreed that time management

allows procurement professionals to organize and enable staff to get more done in less time. Perhaps, the majority also agreed that procurement should be part of the time management strategy of the organization. 95% agreed that maximum productivity is achieved for the organization

through a proactive process of procurement unit to the needs of the organization. Therefore, it shows clearly that time management has a significant relationship with the practice of proactive procurement, and the null hypothesis is strongly rejected while all alternative hypotheses are accepted.

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	.307	.510		.601	.549
Do the organization set a target for each day to serve as a measure for the workers	-.128	.172	-.017	-.744	.458
Do the organization have a long-run organizational goal	.761	.250	.069	3.044	.003
Do the organization enforce supervision of its workers to accomplish the target goals	-.723	.382	-.100	-1.895	.060
Do the organization regularly inform the workers to have a clear idea of its goals	-.223	.200	-.037	-1.117	.265
Does the organization generally adopt time management strategies?	.484	.262	.090	1.850	.066
Do the organization quickly respond to issues that arise unexpectedly	2.484	.426	.283	5.826	.000
Do the organization always implement the time management strategies	7.277	.322	.877	22.606	.000
1. Dependent Variable: Organizational Survival R ² = .395, F (534,12) = 252.3, P value = .000					

Table 7: Regression analysis showing the relationship between time management and organizational going concerned/survival which is the main objective of the study

VI. CONCLUSION

This study examines the effective time management for the survival of 4 big Agricultural farms in Oyo State. The idea behind using Agricultural farms is based on the fact that they are business entities conscious of time to make enough profit to remain on the market. In some SMEs, especially trading companies, arrival time, services time, and waiting time can be measured. This means that managing business also means managing time. The study established a relationship between time management and organization survival.

The study concluded that time management has significant influence on the organization survival.

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